

Table 2.

Questions and scoring from the Uppsala Life and Health Young Cross-sectional Survey (LHS) selected by two independent researchers to represent DSM5

Conduct Disorder (CD) categories.

LHS Question No.	LHS Question (Aggression: people or animals (APA))	LHS Scoring
C5	Have you exposed someone else to bullying, threats or harassment via mobile or SMS?	1=No, 2=One time, 3=Many times
F16	Have you beaten, kicked or exposed someone else to violence during the school term?	1=No, 2=One time, 3=Many times
F18	Have you been annoyed by someone else this semester?	1=No, 2=One time, 3=Many times
G1-12	Have you participated in fights at school?	1=Never, 2=One time, 3=2-4 times, 4=5-10 times, 5=More than 10 times
G1-13	Have you illegally carried a knife or other weapon in school?	1=Never, 2=One time, 3=2-4 times, 4=5-10 times, 5=More than 10 times
G1-14	Have you illegally carried a knife or other weapon in the town?	1=Never, 2=One time, 3=2-4 times, 4=5-10 times, 5=More than 10 times
G1-15	Have you had sex with someone against their will?	1=Never, 2=One time, 3=2-4 times, 4=5-10 times, 5=More than 10 times
G1-16	Have you failed to make a payment at the cinema, cafe, train or bus?	1=Never, 2=One time, 3=2-4 times, 4=5-10 times, 5=More than 10 times
G1-17	Have you threatened or forced someone to do something they didn't want to do?	1=Never, 2=One time, 3=2-4 times, 4=5-10 times, 5=More than 10 times
G1-18	Have you driven a moped, car or motorcycle while drinking alcohol?	1=Never, 2=One time, 3=2-4 times, 4=5-10 times, 5=More than 10 times
G1-19	Did you ever get stopped by the police for something you did?	1=Never, 2=One time, 3=2-4 times, 4=5-10 times, 5=More than 10 times
		Min Score: 11, Max Score: 49
LHS Question No.	LHS Question (Destruction of property (DP))	LHS Scoring
G1-10	Have you deliberately destroyed or been involved in destroying things?	1=Never, 2=One time, 3=2-4 times, 4=5-10 times, 5=More than 10 times
G1-11	Have you been involved in scribbling, graffiti painting or writing something with a marker or spray paint without permission?	1=Never, 2=One time, 3=2-4 times, 4=5-10 times, 5=More than 10 times
		Min Score: 2; Max Score: 10

LHS Question No.	LHS Question (Deceitfulness or theft (DT))	LHS Scoring
G1-1	Do you have or had gambling debts to others?	1=Never, 2=One time, 3=2-4 times, 4=5-10 times, 5=More than 10 times
G1-2	Have you taken goods from a department store, kiosk or store without paying?	1=Never, 2=One time, 3=2-4 times, 4=5-10 times, 5=More than 10 times
G1-3	Have you taken money at home that isn't yours?	1=Never, 2=One time, 3=2-4 times, 4=5-10 times, 5=More than 10 times
G1-4	Have you stolen money or things from any schoolmate?	1=Never, 2=One time, 3=2-4 times, 4=5-10 times, 5=More than 10 times
G1-5	Have you threatened or forced someone to give you money, cell phone, cigarettes or anything else?	1=Never, 2=One time, 3=2-4 times, 4=5-10 times, 5=More than 10 times
G1-6	Have you been involved in making a burglary?	1=Never, 2=One time, 3=2-4 times, 4=5-10 times, 5=More than 10 times
G1-7	Have you stolen a bike?	1=Never, 2=One time, 3=2-4 times, 4=5-10 times, 5=More than 10 times
G1-8	Have you stolen a car?	1=Never, 2=One time, 3=2-4 times, 4=5-10 times, 5=More than 10 times
G1-9	Have you sold or bought something that you knew was stolen?	1=Never, 2=One time, 3=2-4 times, 4=5-10 times, 5=More than 10 times
		Min Score: 9; Max Score: 45
LHS Question No.	LHS Question (Serious violation of rules (SVR))	LHS Scoring
A10-1	How easy is it for you at home to say where you go?	1=Many times, 2=sometimes, 3=not so many times, 4=Never
A10-2	How easy is it for you to work on your schoolwork at home?	1=Many times, 2=sometimes, 3=not so many times, 4=Never
A10-3	How easy is it for you to go home?	1=Many times, 2=sometimes, 3=not so many times, 4=Never
A10-4	How easy is it for you to feel close to your home?	1=Many times, 2=sometimes, 3=not so many times, 4=Never
A10-5	How easy is it for you to sleep at home?	1=Many times, 2=sometimes, 3=not so many times, 4=Never
A10-6	How easy is it for you help at home?	1=Many times, 2=sometimes, 3=not so many times, 4=Never
A10-7	How easy is it for you to be at home when you are not at school?	1=Many times, 2=sometimes, 3=not so many times, 4=Never

- F12 Are you truant from school? 1=No never, 2=yes, once in the term, 3=yes, once in the month, 4=yes, 2-3 times in the month, 5=yes, once a week, 6=yes, more than once a week
- F13 Have you not attended some of your subjects? 1=No, not in any subject, 2=Yes, 1-2 subjects, 3=Yes, 3-4 subjects, 4=Yes, 5 or more subjects
- F14 Have you felt uncomfortable because of fear of falling into trouble during the school day? 1=No, 2=Yes one time, 3=yes, more than one time

Min Score: 10; Max Score: 41

Total CD Min score:32; Max Score: 145

(NB:High score denotes high level of self-reported behavioural issues); CD=Conduct Disorder; Min=Minimum; Max=Maximum; LHS=Life Health Survey Questionnaire

Table 3

Questions and scoring from the Uppsala Life and Health Young Cross-sectional Survey (LHS) that represent Psychosomatic complaints (PSC)

LHS Question No.	LHS Question (Psychological Complaints)	LHS Scoring
B2	How satisfied are you with your life?	1=Very satisfied, 2=Satisfied, 3=Neither satisfied no dissatisfied, 4=Dissatisfied, 5=Very dissatisfied
B5_9	Are you stressed?	1=Never, 2=Rarely, 3=Sometimes, 4=Often, 5=Always
B5_10	Are you nervous?	1=Never, 2=Rarely, 3=Sometimes, 4=Often, 5=Always
B5_11	Are you anxious/worried?	1=Never, 2=Rarely, 3=Sometimes, 4=Often, 5=Always
B5_12	Are you depressed?	1=Never, 2=Rarely, 3=Sometimes, 4=Often, 5=Always
B5_13R	Are you happy	1=Never, 2=Rarely, 3=Sometimes, 4=Often, 5=Always
B7_3	Are you on medication for depression, sleep disorder or anxiety?	1=Never, 2=Some of the time, 3=Daily or almost daily
B8_4	Do you have reading or writing difficulties?	1=No, 2=Yes
B8_5	Do you have a neuropsychiatric disorder, such as ADHD?	1=No, 2=Yes
B9_2	Are you worried about sleep?	1=Never, 2=Rarely, 3=Sometimes, 4=Often, 5=Always
B9_3	Do you get nightmares?	1=Never, 2=Rarely, 3=Sometimes, 4=Often, 5=Always
F20	How does the future look to you?	1=The future looks very bright, 2=The future looks fairly bright, 3=The future looks neither bright nor dark, 4=The future looks somewhat dark, 5=The future looks very dark Min Score: 12 Max Score: 52
LHS Question No.	LHS Question (Somatic Complaints)	
B1	How do you feel?	1=Very good, 2=Good, 3=Neither good nor bad, 4=Bad, 5=Very bad
B5_1	Do you get headache (not migraine)?	1=Never, 2=Rarely, 3=Sometimes, 4=Often, 5=Always
B5_2	Do you get migraine?	1=Never, 2=Rarely, 3=Sometimes, 4=Often, 5=Always
B5_3	Do you get stomach ache?	1=Never, 2=Rarely, 3=Sometimes, 4=Often, 5=Always
B5_4	Do you get ringing in the ears/tinnitus?	1=Never, 2=Rarely, 3=Sometimes, 4=Often, 5=Always
B5_5	Do you get tiredness?	1=Never, 2=Rarely, 3=Sometimes, 4=Often, 5=Always

B5_6	Do you get pain in the neck and shoulders?	1=Never, 2=Rarely, 3=Sometimes, 4=Often, 5=Always
B5_7	Do you get pain in the back and hips?	1=Never, 2=Rarely, 3=Sometimes, 4=Often, 5=Always
B5_8	Do you get pain in the hands/knees/legs/feet?	1=Never, 2=Rarely, 3=Sometimes, 4=Often, 5=Always
B6	How is your dental health?	1=Good, 2=Neither good nor bad, 3=Bad
B7_1	Do you take non-prescription drugs for headaches or other pain?	1=Never, 2=Some of the time, 3=Daily or almost daily
B7_2	Do you take prescriptions for headaches or other pain?	1=Never, 2=Some of the time, 3=Daily or almost daily
B8_1	Do you have hearing loss?	1=No, 2=Yes
B8_2	Do you have a visual impairment that cannot be corrected with glasses?	1=No, 2=Yes
B8_3	Do you have a physical disability?	1=No, 2=Yes
B9_1	Do you have difficulty sleeping?	1=Never, 2=Rarely, 3=Sometimes, 4=Often, 5=Always
B9_4	Are you often tired?	1=Never, 2=Rarely, 3=Sometimes, 4=Often, 5=Always
		Min Score: 17 Max Score: 70
		Total PSC Min Score: 29 Max Score: 122

(NB:High score denotes high level of complaint on each of the domains, R=Reverse scored by the authors); LHS=Life Health Survey Questionnaire

Table 5

LHS scores categorised (by two independent researchers) according to DSM5 CD sub- categories, in terms of low, medium and high scores of self-reported PSC in younger, older and total male and female adolescents (in the total n=3,132 cohort, after exclusions)

	Mean%. [s.d.]																	
	Low PSC						Medium PSC						High PSC					
	Male			Female			Male			Female			Male			Female		
	Young (n=376)	Older (n=344)	Total (n=720)	Young (n=210)	Older (n=171)	Total (n=381)	Young (n=212)	Older (n=223)	Total (n=435)	Young (n=240)	Older (n=238)	Total (n=478)	Young (n=137)	Older (n=168)	Total (n=305)	Young (n=358)	Older (n=455)	Total (n=813)
APA	30.29 [6.34]	29.79 [4.76]	30.05 [5.64]	28.16 [2.30]	28.49 [2.61]	28.31 [2.45]	31.14 [5.85]	31.28 [5.06]	31.21 [5.45]	29.41 [3.28]	29.25 [2.84]	29.33 [3.07]	34.90 [10.95]	33.83 [7.79]	34.31 [9.34]	33.04 [7.43]	31.34 [4.69]	32.09 [6.11]
DT	24.93 [10.25]	25.61 [7.61]	25.26 [9.083]	22.85 [4.59]	23.00 [4.45]	22.92 [4.52]	25.95 [7.93]	26.54 [8.50]	26.25 [8.23]	23.99 [5.14]	23.73 [4.92]	23.86 [5.03]	28.40 [14.47]	28.53 [11.78]	28.47 [13.03]	26.98 [8.69]	26.15 [6.67]	26.51 [7.63]
DP	27.23 [15.76]	27.47 [14.62]	27.35 [15.21]	23.10 [9.41]	23.27 [9.57]	23.18 [9.47]	29.34 [16.28]	30.00 [16.28]	29.68 [16.26]	25.42 [11.85]	24.75 [10.22]	25.08 [11.06]	31.82 [20.19]	31.90 [19.36]	31.87 [19.71]	29.80 [16.42]	26.73 [13.23]	28.08 [14.79]
SVR	42.29 [7.72]	44.98 [8.05]	43.58 [7.99]	38.27 [6.67]	42.66 [7.69]	40.24 [7.46]	42.96 [7.84]	48.44 [9.25]	45.77 [9.01]	39.91 [7.06]	43.72 [8.30]	41.81 [7.93]	46.10 [10.35]	50.01 [10.28]	48.26 [10.48]	44.92 [9.69]	47.50 [9.34]	46.37 [9.58]
Total CD	31.70 [6.79]	32.33 [5.28]	32.00 [6.12]	28.99 [3.13]	30.27 [3.49]	29.57 [3.35]	32.61 [5.82]	34.22 [5.60]	33.44 [5.76]	30.38 [3.77]	31.14 [3.71]	30.76 [3.75]	35.81 [10.36]	36.35 [8.23]	36.11 [9.24]	34.22 [7.26]	33.73 [5.30]	33.94 [6.24]

APA=Aggression to people or animals; DP=Destruction of property; DT=Deception or theft; SVR=Serious violation of rules; N=Number of participants per sub-sample – missing values excluded; s.d.=standard deviation; young=15-16yrs; older=17-19yrs; PSC=Psychosomatic Complaints; Low PSC=0-33 percentile, Medium PSC=34-66 percentile, High PSC=67-100 percentile